

ASSOCIATIONS BETWEEN TECHNICAL TEACHERS' CONCEPTIONS OF, AND APPROACHES TO, ICT-ENHANCED TEACHING AND THEIR CONCEPTIONS OF ICT USE IN THE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

This paper builds upon the authors' previous research on Technical and Further Education (TAFE) teachers' conceptions of (first paper), and approaches to (second paper), ICT-enhanced teaching in professional education (third paper). This paper aims to examine relationships among the above three aspects, that is: between TAFE teachers' conceptions of, and approaches to, ICT-enhanced teaching

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and their associated view about ICT use in the workplace. Phenomenography, a qualitative research approach that emphasizes the importance of people's experience of a phenomenon, was selected as a research methodology for this study. A cohort of 23 teachers from three TAFE institutions in NSW, Australia, participated in semi-structured, in-depth interviews. This study found that teachers' conceptions of, and approaches to, ICT-enhanced teaching, and conceptions of ICT in the workplace are linked. More specifically, TAFE teachers who hold a particular conception of ICT-enhanced teaching tended to adopt related approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching that are further linked with conceptions of ICT in the workplace. TAFE teachers who expressed 'student-centred/activity-oriented and/or industry-oriented' conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching were more likely to adopt a 'student-focused' approach to ICT-enhanced teaching. The teachers within this group were more likely to hold an understanding of the role of ICT in the workplace as an effective or essential tool in professional activities. This paper offers new insights that contribute to bridging the gap between ICT in teaching and ICT in workplace practice. These findings could help develop new initiatives to address the existing gap between teaching in TAFE institutes and current practices in the workplace.

1. INTRODUCTION

Discrepancies between what is taught in engineering education and what is practiced in the industry is a fact that has been reported in the literature [1]. In order to address this claim, the short paper builds upon the authors' previous research on Technical and Further Education (TAFE) teachers' conceptions of, and approaches to, ICT-enhanced teaching in professional education. It investigated three aspects related to ICT use in technical (engineering) education. The first article (published) identified two broad conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching in technical education: (i) teacher-centred conception, which comprises three categories of description: ICT is used to meet external expectations, ICT enables to gain access to information and resources, and ICT is a delivery tool, and (ii) student-centred conception, which includes two categories of description: ICT is a media for active learning, and ICT is a means of preparing students for their future profession [2]. The second article (published) found two broad orientations with five approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching: (i) teacher-focused orientation with three teaching approaches: comprising information-oriented, feedback-oriented, practice-oriented, and (ii) student-focused orientation with two teaching approaches: activity-oriented and industry-oriented teaching [3]. The third article (published), further investigated how TAFE teachers conceptualized the role of ICT use in the workplace and found three conceptions: using ICT for various regular work-related tasks; helping accomplish a job more effectively; and using ICT as an essential tool in professional activities [1]. In order to build a relationship among these three articles (above three aspects), this short paper aims to examine relationships between technical teachers' conceptions of, and approach to, ICT-enhanced teaching and their associated view about ICT use in the workplace. The rest of the short paper is organized into three sections: 'Methodology' explains phenomenographic research approach and brief procedure of the study; 'Results' provides associations among prior studies; 'Discussion and Conclusions' synthesizes the results and discusses its contributions.

2. METHODOLOGY

Phenomenography, a qualitative emerging research approach for engineering education that emphasizes the importance of people's experience of a phenomenon, was selected as a research methodology for this study [4]. In phenomenographic research, it is often depicted as how people understand, perceive, discern, conceive

or experience the aspect of the world around them which is articulated by the one word “conception” [5]. Sample selection, data collection and analysis of data, therefore, was followed by the principle of the phenomenographic approach. A cohort of 23 teachers (P01 to P23) from three TAFE institutions in NSW, Australia, participated in semi-structured, in-depth interviews. Interviews data were transcribed verbatim and analysed by following seven steps, such as *familiarisation, compilation, condensation, preliminary grouping, preliminary comparison of category, naming of the categories, and outcome space* [2]. From this analysis, three outcomes were revealed (i) teachers’ conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching, (ii) teachers’ approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching and (iii) teachers’ conceptions of ICT in the workplace. In the second stage, we identified 23 participants’ dominant attributes(qualities) towards these three findings. Each of the participant’s dominant attributes was placed in the relationships and was built into two relationships: *Associations between conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching and conceptions of ICT in the workplace; and Associations between approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching and conceptions of ICT in the workplace.*

3. RESULTS

This study found that teachers’ conceptions of, and approaches to, ICT-enhanced teaching, and conceptions of ICT in the workplace are linked. Table 1 shows associations between conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching and conceptions of ICT in the workplace for which students are prepared. The associations indicate that the two conceptions are related.

The table 1 presents two areas of association for 21 teachers out of 23 teachers. The first area, circle one (1), conceives of ICT-enhanced teaching as a ‘teacher-centred/content-oriented’ and this is linked with Categories A and B in the workplace. In this area, technical teachers who hold ICT-enhanced teaching as a ‘teacher-centred/content-oriented’, tended to understand the role of ICT in the workplace from supplementary to effective. The second area, circle two (2), perceives ICT-enhanced teaching as ‘student-centred/activity-oriented’ and ‘student-centred/industry-oriented’ conceptions and these conceptions are connected with Categories B and C in the workplace. In this area (2), technical teachers who viewed ICT-enhanced teaching as ‘student-centred/activity-oriented and / or industry-oriented’, tended to understand the role of ICT in the workplace from effective to obligatory in nature. However, two

teachers in this study did not express conceptions that followed the stated associations. Therefore, they were not placed within the two marked areas (See Table 1: P01 and P08).

Table 1 *Associations between conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching and conceptions of ICT in the workplace*

Conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching		Conceptions of ICT in workplace		
		A	B	C
Teacher-centred/ content- oriented	A	P22	1	
	B			
	C	P16, P23	P07, P10, P15, P17, P21	P01
Student-centred/ activity-oriented	D		P11, P18	P02, P03, P04, P14, P19
Student-centred/ industry-oriented	E	P08	P06, P09, P20	P05, P12, P13
Conceptions of ICT-enhanced teaching, ICT is used: (A) to meet external expectations. (B) to gain access to information and resources. (C) as a delivery tool. (D) as a medium for active learning; and (E) for preparing students for their future profession.		Conceptions of ICT in workplace, ICT- (A) could be used for various work-related tasks (supplementary). (B) helps to accomplish a job more effectively (effective); and (C) is an essential tool in professional activities (obligatory).		

The associations indicate that both approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching and conceptions of ICT in the workplace are related (Table 2). The table presents two groups of associated areas for 21 teachers out of 23 teachers. The first group, highlighted as circle one (P1), conceives of approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching as a ‘teacher-focused approaches and this is linked with Categories A and B in the workplace. In this area, technical teachers who hold ICT-enhanced teaching as a ‘teacher-focused’ teaching approach tended to understand the role of ICT in the workplace from supplementary to effective. The second area, marked as circle two (P2), is included under a ‘student-focused approaches’ and these approaches are connected with Categories B and C in the workplace. In P2, technical teachers who viewed ICT-enhanced teaching as a ‘student-focused’ teaching approach, tended to understand the role of ICT in the workplace from effective to obligatory in nature.

Table 2 *Associations between approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching and conceptions of ICT in workplace*

Approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching		Conceptions of ICT in workplace		
		A	B	C
Teacher-focused	A	P22		
	B	P1	P07	P01
	C	P16, P23	P11, P15, P17, P21	
Student-focused	D		P06, P18	P02, P03, P04, P14, P19
	E	P08	P09, P10, P20	P2 P05, P12, P13
<p>Approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching:</p> <p>(A) a teacher-focused, information-oriented strategy with the intention of effectively delivering subject content.</p> <p>(B) a teacher-focused, feedback-oriented strategy with the intention of achieving intended course outcomes.</p> <p>(C) a teacher-focused, practice-oriented strategy with the intention of linking theoretical and practical knowledge.</p> <p>(D) a student-focused, facilitation-oriented strategy with the intention of providing active learning for developing students' understanding; and</p> <p>(E) a student-focused, industry-oriented strategy with the intention of developing students' knowledge and skills to meet the industry's needs.</p>		<p>Conceptions of ICT in workplace, ICT-</p> <p>(A) could be used for various work-related tasks (supplementary).</p> <p>(B) helps to accomplish a job more effectively (effective); and</p> <p>(C) is an essential tool in professional activities (obligatory).</p>		

However, two teachers did not express approaches to teaching that followed the above-stated associations; therefore, they were not placed within the two marked areas (See Table 2: P01 and P08).

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Technical teachers who hold a particular conception of ICT-enhanced teaching tended to adopt related approaches to ICT-enhanced teaching that are further linked with conceptions of ICT in the workplace. The relationships of this paper have an impact on teachers' pedagogical practices in technical education (Tables 1 & Table 2). For

instance, teachers who conceived of ICT as obligatory and effective instruments in the industry are more likely to introduce knowledge and skills related to ICT in their teaching. This means that, the students will be acquainted with using different forms of ICT in the classroom instruction (teaching and learning) that will facilitate them linking with their future workplace (industry). This paper provides further insights that contribute to bridging the existing gap between teaching in technical (engineering) educational institutes and current practices in the industry where there is a particular focus on using ICT. These findings could help improving engineering teacher professional development programs, minimising the existing gap between teaching practices in engineering institutions and real practices in the workplace. The extended elaboration of these associations and the reasons for showing this nature would be discussed in the upcoming journal article.

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